

An Intelligent System for Eco Route Planning of Heavy Duty Vehicles

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Abstract—This work presents a cloud-based system devoted to provide to Heavy-Duty Vehicles (HDVs) the route that guarantees the minimum fuel consumption and the maximum travel time. To this aim, given a specified mission, the Cloud Optimizer builds a route network collecting the main possible routes from the assigned origin to the destination. Moreover, an updated HDV longitudinal model that integrates predictive traffic, weather conditions, road topography and load factor is presented in order to determine the optimized velocity and gear profiles. Finally, the cloud system finds the route that minimizes the fuel consumption and the travel time by finding the minimum path in the weighted route network.

I. EXTENDED ABSTRACT

The automotive industry has made a substantial effort in recent years in developing powertrain technologies to improve fuel efficiency on Heavy-Duty Vehicles (HDVs). Due to increasing road freight traffic, however, projections indicate that total HDV energy use and CO_2 emissions are expected to remain stable at the current level over the long term, if no policy action is taken. This is clearly incompatible with the goal of reducing greenhouse gas emissions from transport by around 60 % below 1990 levels by 2050.

To this aim, Ahn and Rakha [1] investigate the impacts of route choice on vehicle energy consumption and emission rates for different vehicle types. They demonstrate that the faster highway route choice is not always the best from an environmental and energy consumption perspective. For this reason, in the recent years some studies are developing a new environmentally navigation concept called *eco-routing*. The eco-routing is the identification of the most energy-efficient route for a vehicle to travel between two points and is offered as a way in which drivers can reduce fuel consumption [2]. In the simulation results presented in [3], the authors establish that eco-routing systems can reduce the fuel consumption in most cases and quantifies the fuel savings in the range between 3.3 % and 9.3 % with respect to typical travel fastest routes on two large metropolitan networks.

Recently, the eco-routing strategies can take advantage by Information Technology Solution applications, mainly in the area of of Advanced Traveler Information Systems. Now,

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many navigation systems can transmit to the drivers a route selection within a roadway network (shortest and fastest routes, toll routes etc.) that considers traffic data, accident occurrence, congestion.

The presented results [4], [5] aim at determining the optimal route and the velocity profiles that minimize the HDV fuel consumption. This task is realized by specifying a Cloud Optimizer (CO) that is based on the design of three main modules: i) an Eco Route Planner that builds a route graph network that collects the main possible routes from the origin to the destination; ii) an HDV longitudinal model that integrates predictive traffic, weather conditions, road topography including slope and curve radius, information about transport mission such as mission duration time and vehicle configuration; iii) an optimiser that on the basis of the built route graph network and the weights provided by the HDV longitudinal model selects the optimal eco-route minimizing the fuel consumption. The cloud configuration allows obtaining several road data by databases and external data services such as information about the traffic speed limits, road works, weather forecast.

Our approach introduces the following innovations:

- weather conditions are considered to limit and optimize velocity and gear profiles;
- a detailed HDV longitudinal model is proposed and extended to consider traffic and weather conditions as well as curve radius;
- given the pair origin-destination and waypoints an algorithm is proposed to generate automatically a route network using external navigation systems;
- the eco-route is calculated considering the maximum duration time of the HDV mission and minimizing the fuel consumption.

A. The Cloud-Based System Architecture

The presented system architecture consists of a set of software components distributed in two different optimization modules that work in a coordinated fashion under the name of Global Optimizer: the Cloud Computing Optimizer and the On-board Optimizer.

The scheme of Fig. 1 reflects the logical separation of two separated but strongly interconnected systems, the Cloud Computing Optimizer and the On-board Optimizer, respectively operating in a Cloud Computing environment and on the truck.

The Cloud Computing Optimizer (CCO) performs the route planning optimization task in a cloud-based environment. In the cloud system, data from external sources (i.e.,

Fig. 1. Global Optimizer

Fig. 2. Cloud computing optimizer

traffic, weather, maps and topography), mission related data (i.e., waypoints, payload, driver) and real-time data provided by the truck on-board system (i.e., position, speed, consumption, environmental sensors) are ingested and processed. The outputs of the CCO are the best route and the related velocities that allow obtaining the minimum CO₂ consumption.

The On-Board optimizer performs the real-time powertrain calibration in order to minimize the consumption.

The CCO architecture (see Fig. 2) consists of two main blocks: i) the Data Management System (DMS); ii) the Cloud Optimizer (CO).

The DMS is structured to work with big datasets coming from external sources and in real-time from the trucks.

The aim of the CO is to obtain the optimal route that an HDV has to follow, in order to reach its destination, by minimizing the fuel consumption and optimizing the route velocity profiles. The CO determines the *best route* considering all relevant criteria for an efficient truck routing: weather forecast, traffic conditions, fuel consumption, Advanced Driver Assistance System (ADAS) data (e.g. road slopes, curve radius, etc.) and load factor. In order to have this information, the CO is connected to the External Data Services (EDSs) and the dashboard of the Fleet Management Company (FMC) which creates the transport mission for the HDV. In particular, the transport mission data include depar-

Fig. 3. The Route Network Generation (RNG) Algorithm

ture position, waypoints, destination position, truck load and maximum mission duration time. Such data are released by the FMC and transmitted by the mission dashboard to the CO. Moreover, weather forecast, traffic conditions as well as 2D topography, altitude and curve radius are provided to the CO by calling the EDSs. The CO is activated by the mission dashboard when the FMC creates a new mission. Fig. 3 shows the scheme of the described CO structure.

Mainly, the CO is divided into three sub-components:

- the Eco Route Planner (ERP) that builds the route network and the corresponding route graph that links the mission departure, waypoints and destination;
- the Vehicle Longitudinal Model (VLM) that calculates the fuel consumption for each route of the network selected by the ERP considering ADAS data, traffic and weather conditions, and load factor;
- the Route Optimizer (RO) that determines the best route based on the minimum fuel consumption and optimal velocity profile.

Some case studies show the efficiency of the proposed cloud system, comparing the fastest routes and regular velocity profiles with the best route and the optimal velocity profiles determined by the CO.

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